

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A pan-Arctic perspective on the influence of ice algae on sea-ice nutrient concentrations

Fowzia Ahmed^{1,*} , Eva Leu², Andrew R. Juhl³, Karley Campbell⁴, Kyle B. Dilliaine⁵, Philipp Assmy⁶, Andrea Niemi⁷, Rolf Gradinger⁴, Eva Alou-Font⁸, Sinhué Torres-Valdés⁹, Laura Whitmore¹⁰, Elizabeth M. Jones¹¹, Agneta Fransson⁶, Melissa Chierici¹¹, Lasse Mork Olsen^{12,13}, Rosalie Dawn McKay⁴, Sang H. Lee¹⁴, Marc Oggier¹⁰, Benjamin A. Lange¹⁵, Jean-Éric Tremblay¹⁶, Michel Gosselin¹⁷, and C. J. Mundy¹

Sea-ice algae account for a substantial part of annual primary production in ice-covered waters and are an important component of the Arctic marine food web. With climate-induced changes to snow and sea-ice cover and their impact on the surface ocean, such as earlier melt, thinner ice, and increased upper-ocean stratification, a shift toward earlier and more extensive nutrient limitation on ice algal growth can be expected. Therefore, increasing our understanding of the processes governing nutrient supply and uptake by sea-ice algae is essential. Here, we compiled a pan-Arctic dataset of concentrations of sea-ice and sub-ice nutrients and sea-ice chlorophyll *a* (chl *a*) to assess their regional and seasonal variability, as well as the relationship of sea-ice algae and nutrient dynamics in the Arctic Ocean. This dataset indicates that bottom sea-ice nutrient and chl *a* concentrations were highest in the central Canadian Arctic Archipelago (Resolute Passage) due to tidal-driven mixing at the ocean-ice interface, and lowest in the Arctic Ocean basins. At the regional scale, Pacific and Atlantic Water influence variability in sea-ice and sub-ice nutrient concentrations. Significant positive relationships of bottom sea-ice nutrient versus chl *a* concentrations were ubiquitous across the Arctic during the ice algal bloom, suggesting intracellular nutrient storage as an important mechanism to support ice algal growth. This relationship in turn alters nutrient ratios within the sea ice relative to sub-ice waters, decreasing NO_x:PO₄ ratios, while increasing NO_x:Si(OH)₄ ratios. In contrast, bottom sea-ice nutrient-chl *a* relationships were less common and sometimes negative when nutrient concentrations were low, likely reflecting nutrient limitation. In conclusion, we have demonstrated a pan-Arctic, yet regionally specific, influence of the ice algal community on bottom sea-ice nutrient concentrations.

Keywords: Nutrients, Sea-ice algae, Arctic

1. Introduction

Sea-ice algae can account for up to 25% of total annual primary production in Arctic seas covered seasonally by

first-year sea ice (Legendre et al., 1992; Hegseth, 1998) and can contribute 68%–86% of annual primary production in the central Arctic Ocean covered by multiyear ice

¹Centre for Earth Observation Science, Clayton H. Riddell Faculty of Environment, Earth, and Resources, University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

²Akvaplan-niva, Fram Centre, Tromsø, Norway

³Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory of Columbia University, Palisades, NY, USA

⁴Department of Arctic and Marine Biology, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Tromsø, Norway

⁵College of Fisheries and Ocean Sciences, University of Alaska Fairbanks, Fairbanks, AK, USA

⁶Norwegian Polar Institute, Fram Centre, Tromsø, Norway

⁷Fisheries and Oceans Canada, Arctic Region, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

⁸Marine Science Program, Biological and Environmental Science and Engineering Division, BESE, KAUST—King Abdullah University of Science and Technology, Thuwal, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

⁹Alfred-Wegener-Institute, Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung, Bremerhaven, Germany

¹⁰International Arctic Research Center, University of Alaska Fairbanks, Fairbanks, AK, USA

¹¹Institute of Marine Research, Tromsø, Norway

¹²Aqua Kompetanse, Flatanger, Norway

¹³Department of Bioscience, University of Bergen, Bergen, Norway

¹⁴Department of Oceanography and Marine Research Institute, Pusan National University, Busan, South Korea

¹⁵Norwegian Geotechnical Institute, Oslo, Norway

¹⁶Québec-Océan and Takuvik, Département de biologie, Université Laval, Québec, QC, Canada

¹⁷Québec-Océan and Institut des sciences de la mer, Université du Québec à Rimouski, Rimouski, QC, Canada

*Corresponding author:
Email: ahmedf6@myumanitoba.ca

(Gosselin et al., 1997). Ice algae also play a critical trophic role as an early first pulse of energy to the Arctic marine food web (Soreide et al., 2006; Kohlbach et al., 2016; Amiraux et al., 2023; Niemi et al., 2024). A change in ice algal biomass and production is expected with climate warming; however, the magnitude of this change will depend on variations in the environmental factors that regulate primary production (Leu et al., 2015; Tedesco et al., 2019; Lannuzel et al., 2020). For example, increasing air temperatures in Arctic regions have delayed freeze-up and extended the melt season (Markus et al., 2009), which results in a shortened ice growth period leading to younger and thinner sea ice (Stroeve et al., 2012; Stroeve and Notz, 2018; Landy et al., 2022) with less accumulated snow cover (Webster et al., 2014). The resultant thinner snow and ice cover acts to increase growth of ice algae due to decreased light limitation, yet earlier ice melt contributes to earlier bloom termination (Leu et al., 2015; Niemi et al., 2024; Yendamuri et al., 2024). In addition to timing of the bloom, the magnitude of ice melt also enhances upper-ocean stratification, which could increase nutrient limitation by decreasing ocean-ice nutrient fluxes to ice algae (Lannuzel et al., 2020). These different scenarios highlight a need for information on nutrient dynamics in sea ice that is broadly applicable across Arctic regions to better understand how the ecological and biogeochemical importance of ice algae will respond to changes in the icescape.

Growth and community composition of bottom sea-ice algae are influenced by light availability and nutrient supply (Leu et al., 2015; van Leeuwe et al., 2018), where nitrate (NO_3^-), ammonium (NH_4^+), phosphate (PO_4^{3-}), and silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$) are critical macronutrients for ice algal growth. Ice algae mainly access nutrients from the water column, where ocean-ice nutrient fluxes to the community are largely driven by the strength of ocean-ice shear, associated turbulence, and vertical nutrient gradients (Gosselin et al., 1985; Dalman et al., 2019; Duarte et al., 2021). Nutrient availability to ice algae is augmented via salt segregation and brine-driven convection (Reeburgh, 1984), as well as re-mineralization of organic matter, such as extracellular products from bacteria and meiofaunal excreta, although the relative contribution of these supplies are highly variable and sometimes minor relative to the ocean-ice flux (Cota et al., 1987). Nutrient sources for both pack and landfast ice are similar; however, landfast ice tends to have enhanced nutrient exchange relative to pack ice because landfast ice commonly forms in shallow water over continental shelves where nutrient exchange is enhanced (Mahoney et al., 2007; Weingartner et al., 2017). Higher nutrient concentrations in landfast ice are also influenced by other factors, including terrestrial runoff (Carmack et al., 2015) and nutrient supply from benthic processes (Rysgaard et al., 2008).

Sea ice is a complex structure containing solid ice, liquid brine, solid salts, and gas (Weeks, 2010). Nutrients within sea ice, in the form of dissolved inorganic ions and organic molecules, exist within the brine where temperature directly influences the concentration of salt ions and

other moieties, an exception being NH_4 which potentially can be incorporated into the ice crystal structure during freezing (Thomas et al., 2010; Fransson et al., 2013). Furthermore, as temperatures decrease above the accreting ice bottom due to thermodynamic ice growth, sea-ice permeability decreases rapidly, limiting the exchange of brine with new nutrients from the underlying water column to the bottommost centimeters of the sea ice (Golden et al., 2007). Therefore, the bottom layer of sea ice provides a permeable habitat of high interior surface area that is close to ambient ocean conditions with respect to temperature and salinity (Mundy and Meiners, 2021). Most of the spring Arctic ice algal biomass and production is observed within this bottom-ice habitat (Smith et al., 1990; Juhl et al., 2011; Leu et al., 2015). As a result, most Arctic ice algal studies focus on the lowermost layer of sea ice.

Nutrient samples of the sea-ice environment are typically collected from ice cores sectioned in the field and immediately stored in bags or sterile containers to limit brine loss (Miller et al., 2015). Proper sample handling is critical to preserving natural concentrations of nutrients; however, subsequent processing steps, such as melting the ice, can introduce biases. During ice melting, the decrease in salinity can cause osmotic stress on algal cells (Garrison and Buck, 1986; Campbell et al., 2019), likely leading to a release of intracellular nutrients (Cota and Horne, 1989; Mundy et al., 2025). Another approach to quantify nutrient concentrations is to directly sample brine via sack holes, where brine from the surrounding ice drains into a partially cored hole (Miller et al., 2015). Samples collected via this method are likely less affected by osmotic stress; however, this method cannot account for the origin of the brine within the sea-ice matrix or the biological material adhering to brine channel walls. An additional method of collecting brine samples is to centrifuge ice core sections which allows for brine processing from discrete layers (Manes and Gradinger, 2009; McMinin et al., 2009; Munro et al., 2010). However, this method is rarely employed, likely due to logistical constraints and the potential alteration of dissolved sea-ice constituents from centrifugation. There remains a notable lack of studies systematically comparing methodologies of brine sampling, leaving gaps in understanding the potential biases introduced by these approaches.

The Arctic Ocean is a unique and complex system characterized by large regional variability, with dynamic processes influencing nutrient availability to sea ice. Although many studies have investigated nutrient concentrations in Arctic sea ice, a pan-Arctic perspective on nutrient availability for ice algae is not available. Here, we compiled a large collection of data on concentrations of sea-ice and sub-ice nutrients and sea-ice chlorophyll *a* (chl *a*) from both landfast and pack ice in the Arctic Ocean. Our goal was to assess the regional and seasonal variability of sea-ice and sub-ice nutrient concentrations and ratios across the pan-Arctic by focusing on regional differences in nutrient sources and associated processes and by examining the patterns of nutrient availability to sea-ice algae across the Arctic Ocean.

2. Methods

Data from 30 published and unpublished datasets collected between 1983 and 2023 in Arctic sea-ice regions were collated for this study (**Table 1**). Studies were included if they reported bottom sea-ice chl *a* and nutrient concentrations. Some datasets were excluded because the data were not available in extractable format. Most datasets were collected during spring and summer (March–July), with only 5.2% and 1.4% of samples collected in winter (November–February) and in autumn (August–October), respectively. All the data included were from first-year ice, as confirmed by field observations, for example, ice thickness (typically <2 m) and sampling timing relative to the annual ice growth cycle reported in the original studies. Data were compiled from both landfast and pack ice, with 20 studies of only landfast ice, eight studies of only pack ice, and two studies that had a combination of landfast and pack ice (Alou-Font et al., 2013; Lange et al., 2015); a part of one study was from a coastal lagoon (Manes and Gradinger, 2009). All sampling sites were grouped into five Arctic shelf/basin areas that were further subdivided into 14 regions based on geographical proximity (**Table 2**). Within the Canadian Arctic Archipelago (CAA) region, Cambridge Bay and Resolute Passage were treated as separate subgroups, due to their distinct geographical features, and discussed separately throughout the paper. Samples collected near the North Pole were combined with the Amundsen Basin dataset. Most of the studies were restricted to an individual region; however, four drifting expeditions were divided into different regions (**Table 1**). The locations of all collated studies are shown in **Figure 1**.

2.1. Nutrient concentrations

Sea-ice nutrient concentrations (NO_3 , NH_4 , PO_4 , and $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$) were measured from the bottommost ice core sections. Thickness of the bottommost sections ranged between 3 cm and 10 cm, with two studies including the bottom 20 cm (**Table 1**). A total of 38 complete vertical profiles of sea-ice nutrient concentrations were also compiled where data were available. The general procedure of collecting ice cores for nutrient analysis used an ice corer with a core barrel of internal diameter ranging from 7.5 cm to 14 cm. The extracted ice cores were cut into sections and melted in the dark at ambient temperatures resulting in varying melting rates across studies. A few bottom-ice profiles used a novel in situ sampler, with the ice core retrieved from the sampler chamber then cut into 2 mm sections using an electric meat cutter (Smith et al., 1990). Data from water samples at the ocean-ice interface and 2 m depth were also compiled. These samples were collected via a submersible pump or hand-held water sampler; they are referred to collectively as sub-ice samples and were used for comparative purposes.

Samples for determination of dissolved inorganic nutrient concentrations were either analyzed directly on the melted ice sample (unfiltered) or its filtrate (filtered through sterile 0.2 μm pore membrane filters or through combusted glass-fiber filters; **Tables 1** and S1). The difference between these two approaches can be significant in

nutrient samples from sea ice containing high algal biomass. Samples were commonly kept frozen at -20°C until analysis, while one study stored them at -80°C prior to analysis (Rózańska et al., 2009). Some samples were poisoned with mercuric chloride before storing, while two studies fixed samples with 0.2 mL chloroform prior to storage (Olsen et al., 2017; Fransson et al., 2025; Jones et al., 2025). Previous studies found no significant difference between samples stored frozen or treated with poison prior to analyses versus those analyzed as soon as collected (Kattner, 1999; Gundersen et al., 2022). However, storing NH_4 samples impacts the concentration (Degobbi, 1973), and therefore, these samples were typically measured in the field. Nutrient concentrations were measured mainly with automated or manual colorimetric methods (Strickland and Parsons, 1972; Grasshoff et al., 1999; Gundersen et al., 2022). Some studies reported dissolved nitrogen concentration as $\text{NO}_3 + \text{NO}_2$ (nitrate + nitrite), while others reported NO_3 only. Due to very low NO_2 concentrations in Arctic waters (Pineault et al., 2013; Tuerena et al., 2022), here we refer to $\text{NO}_3 + \text{NO}_2$ and NO_3 as NO_x (i.e., oxidized nitrogen species). Only a few studies analyzed NH_4 concentrations using the orthophthalaldehyde or the manual phenolphthorite methods (Bower and Holm-Hansen, 1980; Holmes et al., 1999).

2.2. Chlorophyll *a* measurements

Chl *a* concentrations were analyzed mainly from the bottommost section of sea-ice cores, which ranged from 3 cm to 20 cm in length depending on the study, while four studies assessed multiple core sections to characterize the vertical distribution of chl *a* throughout the sea ice (**Table 1**). After collecting the bottom-ice cores, filtered seawater (FSW) was added to most of the ice core sections before melting to minimize osmotic shock (Garrison and Buck, 1986). However, some of the studies did not add FSW during melting (**Table 1**). Prior studies found no difference in chl *a* concentration between ice samples melted with or without the addition of FSW (Cota et al., 1990); therefore, all chl *a* data were compiled within the dataset, regardless of method. When samples for determination of chl *a* concentrations were analyzed at a later date, filters were stored at -20°C to -80°C . The most common approach was to extract pigments from filters using 90% acetone or 100% methanol for quantification using the fluorometric method (Table S1). A few studies used high-performance liquid chromatography to analyze pigments (excluding phaeopigments and allomers) and calculated total chl *a*, which is also considered as chl *a* in this study. All chl *a* concentrations were expressed in mg m^{-2} ; for studies reporting values in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, concentrations were converted using the specific sampled ice thickness reported in each study.

2.3. Statistical analyses

All statistical analyses were performed using R (version 4.4.2) and R Studio (version 2024.12.1+563). Variables extracted from publications as average values were not included in any statistical tests. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to test for normality of the data. For normally

Table 1. Overview of datasets on sea-ice nutrient and chl *a* concentrations collated in this study

Region (campaign name)	Year	Ice type	Bottom-ice thickness (cm)	Filtered for nutrient analysis	Added FSW for chl <i>a</i>	References
Chukchi Sea	2002	Pack	10	No	No	Gradinger (2009a)
Chukchi Sea	2004	Pack	10	No	No	Gradinger (2009b)
Coastal Alaska	2003	Landfast	Full core ^a	No	No	Lee et al. (2008)
Coastal Alaska	2001–2006	Landfast	Full core ^a	Yes	No	Eddie et al. (2010), Juhl et al. (2011), Aumack et al. (2014), and Juhl and Krembs (n.d.)
Coastal Alaska	2005–2006	Landfast	20	NA ^b	No	Manes and Gradinger (2009)
Coastal Alaska	2011–2012	Landfast	Full core ^a	Yes	Yes	Juhl and Aumack (n.d.)
Coastal Alaska	2021	Landfast	10	Yes	Yes	Whitmore et al. (2024) and Dilliplaine et al. (2025)
Canada Basin	1997–1998	Pack	10	No	No	Melnikov et al. (2002)
Beaufort Sea	2004	Landfast	4	Yes	Yes	Riedel et al. (2008) and Rózańska et al. (2008)
Beaufort Sea	2008	Landfast, pack	3	Yes	Yes	Alou-Font et al. (2013)
Resolute Passage	1983–1985	Landfast	5	No	No	Cota et al. (1990)
Resolute Passage	1986–1987	Landfast	Full core ^a	Yes	Yes	Smith et al. (1990)
Resolute Passage	2010–2012	Landfast	3	Yes	Yes	Galindo et al. (2014); (2016) and Mundy et al. (2014); (2025)
Cambridge Bay	2014	Landfast	5	Yes	Yes	Campbell et al. (2016)
Cambridge Bay	2016	Landfast	5	Yes	Yes	Dalman et al. (2019)
Cambridge Bay	2017	Landfast	10	Yes	No	Kim et al. (2020)
Cambridge Bay	2018	Landfast	10	Yes	No	Kim et al. (2023)
Cambridge Bay	2022	Landfast	10	Yes	Yes	McKay et al. (2025a)
Lincoln Sea	2010, 2012	Landfast, pack	10	NA ^b	No	Lange et al. (2015)
Baffin Bay	2015–2016	Landfast	3	Yes	Yes	Oziel et al. (2019) and Massicotte et al. (2020)
Greenland fjord	2010	Landfast	3	Yes	Yes	Sogaard et al. (2013)
Greenland fjord	2012	Landfast	5	Yes	NA ^b	Sogaard et al. (2019)
Greenland fjord	2017	Landfast	10	NA ^b	NA ^b	Sogaard et al. (2021)
Svalbard fjord	2017	Landfast	3	Yes	Yes	Brown et al. (2020), Leu et al. (2020), and Kvernvik et al. (2021)
Svalbard fjord	2021	Landfast	3	Yes	Yes	Forgereau et al. (2023)
Yermak Plateau and Nansen Basin (N-ICE)	2015	Pack	10	No	No	Olsen et al. (2017)
Nansen Basin, Amundsen Basin and Barents Sea (Nansen Legacy)	2021	Pack	10	No	Yes	Vader and Marquardt (2022), Chierici and Fransson (2025), Fransson et al. (2025), and Jones et al. (2025)

Table 1. (continued)

Region (campaign name)	Year	Ice type	Bottom-ice thickness (cm)	Filtered for nutrient analysis	Added FSW for chl <i>a</i>	References
Amundsen and Nansen basins, Yermak Plateau (MOSaIC)	2019–2020	Pack	5	Yes	Yes	Oggier et al. (2024), Salganik et al. (2024), and Torres-Valdés et al. (2024)
Amundsen and Nansen basins (Arctic Ocean 2022)	2022	Pack	5	Yes	Yes	Campbell and Osanen (2025)
Barents Sea	2023	Pack	5	Yes	Yes	McKay et al. (2025b)

^aFull vertical sea-ice profile was included in the dataset only for **Figures 5** and **6**.

^bNA = Not available.

distributed data, a Student's t-test was performed to test for significant differences between means. For non-normally distributed data, Mann-Whitney U or Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to identify significant differences. When significant differences were identified by Kruskal-Wallis tests, pairwise multiple comparisons were performed as a post hoc test using Dunn's method with a Bonferroni correction. Pearson's correlation was used for normally distributed variables, while Spearman's rank correlation was applied to non-normally distributed data.

3. Results

3.1. Regional variability of nutrient and bottom-ice chl *a* concentrations

High regional variability of bottom-ice chl *a* and nutrient (bottom-ice and sub-ice) concentrations was observed within the compiled data set (**Figure 2** and **Table 2**). There was also interannual and seasonal variability within regions where multiple studies were conducted (Table S2). All number of observations (*n*) corresponding to the means and standard deviations reported in this section are provided in the tables cited in the text.

In the Pacific inflow shelf area, average (\pm standard deviation) sea-ice chl *a* concentrations in the Chukchi Sea and coastal Alaska considered separately were $4.46 \pm 10.59 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$ and $6.00 \pm 13.00 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$, respectively (Table S3). Among studies that included NH_4 measurements, the highest average bottom-ice NH_4 concentration was observed in coastal Alaska ($2.22 \pm 2.32 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$; Table S3). Similarly, sub-ice PO_4 concentrations were highest in the Chukchi Sea samples ($2.18 \pm 1.71 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$; Table S3). Si(OH)_4 concentrations were also the highest in Pacific inflow shelf samples in both bottom ice and sub-ice waters among all Arctic regions, with the highest average value observed in the Chukchi Sea for bottom ice ($10.1 \pm 11.9 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and in coastal Alaska for sub-ice waters ($14.4 \pm 7.41 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$; Table S3). Sub-ice Si(OH)_4 concentrations in the Pacific inflow shelves were significantly higher than in other Arctic shelves/basins (pairwise multiple comparisons; Table S4).

The highest average sea-ice chl *a* concentrations were observed in the interior shelves ($9.61 \pm 14.7 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$; **Table 2**). Resolute Passage had the highest average chl *a* ($20.27 \pm 22.95 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$) and bottom-ice NO_x concentrations ($9.72 \pm 12.3 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) among all regions in the Arctic (Table S3). Despite being located in the CAA, NO_x concentrations in sub-ice waters of Cambridge Bay were significantly lower than in Resolute Passage (pairwise multiple comparisons; Table S3) but showed the highest sub-ice NH_4 concentrations compared to other Arctic regions. In the interior shelves, average NO_x and PO_4 concentrations were generally higher in sea ice than in sub-ice water, except in Cambridge Bay for NO_x and the Lincoln Sea for PO_4 (Table S3).

Outflow shelves had significantly greater bottom-ice NO_x concentrations ($4.97 \pm 6.32 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$; **Table 2**) than that of other shelves/basins, except for the interior shelves (pairwise multiple comparison; Table S4). Within the outflow shelf area, Baffin Bay had greater average bottom-ice chl *a* and nutrient concentrations than Greenland fjord in both bottom-ice and sub-ice nutrient samples. Bottom-ice PO_4 and sub-ice NO_x concentrations were significantly lower in Greenland fjord than Baffin Bay (pairwise multiple comparisons; Table S3).

The highest average sub-ice NO_x concentration was observed in the Atlantic inflow shelf relative to all shelves/basins. However, the lowest average Si(OH)_4 concentrations were observed in bottom-ice and sub-ice water samples from the Atlantic inflow shelves, which were significantly lower than all shelves/basins except the Arctic basin (pairwise multiple comparison; Table S4). Yermak Plateau had the lowest average Si(OH)_4 concentrations in sub-ice waters ($3.33 \pm 0.63 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$; Table S3) among all Arctic regions.

The lowest sea-ice chl *a* concentrations were observed in the central Arctic Basin, particularly in the Canada Basin. Furthermore, average NO_x concentrations in bottom ice of the Arctic basin samples were significantly lower than all Arctic shelf/basin areas, except the Pacific inflow shelves (pairwise multiple comparisons; Table S4). The Amundsen Basin had the lowest average bottom-ice

Table 2. Average concentrations (mean \pm standard deviation, n values) of bottom-ice chl a and nutrients and of sub-ice nutrients for Arctic shelves and basins^a

Arctic Shelves/Basins	Bottom-Ice chl a				Bottom-Ice Nutrients ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)				Sub-Ice Nutrients ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)				
	(mg m^{-2})	NO_x	NH_4	PO_4	Si(OH)_4	NO_x	NH_4	PO_4	Si(OH)_4	NO_x	NH_4	PO_4	Si(OH)_4
Pacific inflow shelf ^b (Chukchi Sea and coastal Alaska)	6.18 \pm 12.54, $n = 105$	2.58 \pm 6.3, $n = 63$	2.07 \pm 2.46, $n = 69$	1.74 \pm 2.55, $n = 67$	5.82 \pm 7.3, $n = 81$	4.56 \pm 3.55, $n = 50$	0.72 \pm 0.89, $n = 39$	1.29 \pm 0.95, $n = 51$	13.09 \pm 7.61, $n = 55$				
Interior shelf ^b (Beaufort Sea, CAA and Lincoln Sea)	9.61 \pm 14.7, $n = 263$	4.25 \pm 7.73, $n = 252$	1.35 \pm 1.04, $n = 53$	2.72 \pm 3.98, $n = 251$	3.88 \pm 4.41, $n = 245$	4.07 \pm 3.15, $n = 189$	1.09 \pm 0.95, $n = 25$	0.89 \pm 0.35, $n = 189$	8.44 \pm 4.27, $n = 189$				
Outflow shelf (Baffin Bay and Greenland fjords)	6.67 \pm 8.18, $n = 105$	4.97 \pm 6.32, $n = 97$	0.88 \pm 0.49, $n = 22$	1.48 \pm 1.79, $n = 104$	5.58 \pm 11.5, $n = 98$	3.74 \pm 1.72, $n = 63$	NA ^c	0.75 \pm 0.18, $n = 63$	6.11 \pm 1.08, $n = 58$				
Atlantic inflow shelf (Svalbard fjords, Barents Sea and Yermak Plateau)	3.31 \pm 2.87, $n = 64$	3.96 \pm 4.87, $n = 58$	0.46 \pm 0.39, $n = 2$	0.73 \pm 0.58, $n = 57$	0.56 \pm 0.52, $n = 51$	5.27 \pm 2.78, $n = 43$	0.23 \pm 0.1, $n = 29$	0.50 \pm 0.15, $n = 43$	3.43 \pm 0.67, $n = 43$				
Arctic basin ^b (Canada, Nansen and Amundsen basins)	0.05 \pm 0.08, $n = 34$	0.90 \pm 2.31, $n = 26$	0.61 \pm 0.36, $n = 13$	0.11 \pm 0.07, $n = 26$	0.67 \pm 0.4, $n = 25$	2.40 \pm 3.67, $n = 10$	0.34 \pm 0.16, $n = 2$	0.63 \pm 0.38, $n = 10$	4.21 \pm 2.2, $n = 10$				

^aA Kruskal-Wallis test with H statistic, p -values, and a pairwise multiple comparisons (Dunn's method) between pairs of Arctic shelves/basins and regions are presented in Table S4 and Table S3, respectively; average and standard deviation for each region and each study are presented in Table S3 and Table S2, respectively.

^bData collected from November to February included for Pacific inflow shelf ($n = 17$), interior shelf ($n = 6$), and Arctic basins ($n = 16$).

^cNA = Not available.

Figure 1. Map of the Arctic Ocean showing locations of studies included in the dataset. The oval shapes indicate different Arctic shelves and the Arctic basin. Bathymetry is represented by the color bar (depths in meters).

and sub-ice water NO_x concentrations among regions; however, $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ was comparatively higher in sub-ice waters.

$\text{NO}_x:\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ and $\text{NO}_x:\text{PO}_4$ molar ratios, hereinafter N:Si and N:P, respectively, from bottom ice and sub-ice waters are presented in Table S5. Bottom-ice ratios of N:Si were significantly greater than sub-ice ratios in 9 of 18 studies where a statistical test was possible. In general, the Chukchi Sea and coastal Alaskan sites displayed the least difference between bottom-ice and sub-ice ratios, whereas the highest N:Si ratio as well as the greatest variability in the ratio was documented in the Svalbard bottom-ice samples. The N:P ratio showed an opposite pattern, having greater values in sub-ice than bottom ice, with the difference being significant in 7 of the studies. The highest N:P ratios were observed in bottom-ice and sub-ice samples from Nansen Basin (18.17 ± 29.63) and Svalbard fjord (12.26 ± 0.63), respectively, whereas the lowest N:P ratios were observed in a Greenland fjord for bottom ice (0.23 ± 0.23) and in Amundsen Basin for sub-ice samples (0.28 ± 0.11 ; Table S5).

3.2. Seasonal variation in chl *a* versus nutrient concentrations in bottom sea ice

Seasonal variability in bottom-ice chl *a* and bottom-ice nutrient concentrations (Figure 3) from different regions in the Arctic were observed, with data binned based on 10-day averages. The earliest peak in bottom-ice chl *a* was observed in coastal Alaska (early May), and the final peak was observed in Baffin Bay (early June). Consistently higher chl *a* concentrations were observed in Resolute Passage during mid- to late-May relative to the other regions. Cambridge Bay had the lowest chl *a* concentrations ($8.70 \pm 6.62 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$, $n = 12$) during the peak periods compared to the other areas.

Bottom-ice NO_x concentrations followed the same increasing trend in spring as chl *a* concentrations. For example, the highest 10-day average bottom-ice NO_x concentrations ($16.07 \pm 12.41 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, $n = 9$) were observed during the same time period (May 12–22) when chl *a* concentrations were the highest in Resolute Passage. Correspondingly, there were significant positive correlations between bottom-ice NO_x and chl *a* concentrations in most studies (Figure 4).

Figure 2. Regional distribution of bottom-ice chl *a* and nutrient concentrations in the Arctic Ocean. (a) Bottom sea-ice chl *a* concentrations; (b) bottom-ice NH₄ concentrations; and (c) NO_x, PO₄, and Si(OH)₄ concentrations in bottom-ice (left) and sub-ice samples (right). Boxplots summarize the distribution of observations, where the boxes represent the interquartile range (25th–75th percentile), the horizontal line inside each box shows the median, and the whiskers extend to 1.5 times the interquartile range; values beyond this range are shown as outliers (dots). Missing datasets are noted as not available (NA).

However, Cambridge Bay exhibited a slightly different temporal pattern with respect to corresponding chl *a* and NO_x concentrations. In Cambridge Bay, bottom-ice NO_x

concentrations remained stable initially in April, then started to decrease significantly around May 12–21 (pair-wise multiple comparisons; Table S6), and continued to

Figure 3. Seasonal variation of bottom-ice chl *a* and bottom-ice nutrient concentrations by Arctic region. Each point represents a 10-day average. Error bars indicate standard deviation; *n* values are provided in Table S7. Note that all vertical axes are log scale. Seasonal variation of sub-ice nutrient concentrations is presented in Figure S1.

decline toward the end of the season. Correspondingly, chl *a* concentrations in Cambridge Bay increased until early May, followed by a slight decline or stabilization through

the end of the period. This slightly differing seasonal pattern resulted in no significant correlation to a significant negative correlation observed in 2014 (Figure 4). In contrast, chl

Figure 4. Spearman's rank correlation between bottom-ice chl *a* and nutrient concentrations by Arctic region and year. The color bar at the bottom represents a correlation coefficient scale ranging from -1 to 1 . All correlations were significant ($p < 0.05$) unless noted as not significant (NS, $p > 0.05$) or data not available (NA). This analysis included studies with a sample size of 7 or greater and samples collected between March and July.

a and bottom-ice NO_x concentrations showed mostly significant positive correlations among the different studies (Figure 4), further supported by regression analysis (Table S8).

The bottom-ice PO₄ concentrations showed similar trends of increasing bottom-ice chl *a* concentrations with bloom progression and decreasing concentrations into the post bloom (i.e., decline of chl *a*) phases. Indeed, significant positive correlations between chl *a* and bottom-ice PO₄ concentrations existed in all but one of the studies compiled (Figure 4). Furthermore, significant positive relationships were found through regression analysis in 15 of 21 studies (Table S8). The highest average bottom-ice PO₄ concentrations were observed in Resolute Passage ($7.84 \pm 6.33 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, $n = 9$) and the Beaufort Sea ($12.21 \pm 6.88 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, $n = 8$) during the same time periods as peak 10-day-averaged chl *a* concentrations. However, in coastal Alaska, bottom-ice PO₄ concentrations started to decline earlier (early May) than the declining bloom (mid-May). In Cambridge Bay, PO₄ concentrations in bottom ice stabilized after May 2 when chl *a* concentrations also stabilized.

The bottom-ice Si(OH)₄ concentrations increased as the ice algal bloom progressed; however, the increase was not as steep as in NO_x and PO₄ concentrations. Furthermore, peak concentrations did not align consistently with chl *a* peaks across all regions, except for coastal Alaska. For example, the highest 10-day-average bottom-ice Si(OH)₄ concentrations were observed in Baffin Bay ($14.44 \pm 27.09 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, $n = 11$) in mid-May, while chl *a* concentrations peaked in early June. A significant positive correlation between bottom-ice Si(OH)₄ and chl *a* concentrations was observed in 8 of 15 studies (Figure 4).

NH₄ concentrations were not available across all studies. The highest 10-day-average bottom-ice NH₄ concentrations were observed in coastal Alaska ($3.54 \pm 2.65 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, $n = 6$) during mid-April to early May, with levels remaining steady throughout the season. However, a trend of increasing NH₄ concentrations was recorded alongside development of the ice algal bloom in the Beaufort Sea, where the highest 10-day average concentration ($2.53 \pm 0.91 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, $n = 6$) was observed in early May. In Cambridge Bay, NH₄ concentrations started to decrease as the bloom progressed.

3.3. Vertical variability in sea-ice chl *a* and NO_x concentrations

Vertical sea-ice profiles of chl *a* and NO_x concentrations and sea-ice salinity from coastal Alaska are shown in Figure 5. During winter, when chl *a* concentrations were relatively low, NO_x concentrations roughly followed the sea-ice salinity profile. In contrast, during spring, a sharp increase in chl *a* concentrations in the bottommost layer of the sea ice corresponded to a similar increase in NO_x concentrations. Finer vertical resolution of bottom-ice chl *a* and NO_x concentrations, observed during the ice algal bloom in Resolute Passage, shows a nonlinear increase in both chl *a* and NO_x toward the bottommost centimeters of the sea ice (Figure 6), although the sampling dates between variables were not the same. Chl *a* concentrations were two orders of magnitude greater than that plotted in Figure 5 from the coastal Alaskan study. Approximately 30 mg L^{-1} of chl *a* were concentrated in the bottommost 2 mm of sea ice, which is exceptionally high. Similarly,

Figure 5. Vertical sea-ice profiles of chl *a* concentrations, NO_x concentrations, and salinity from coastal Alaska. Data are presented as normalized ice core depth, defined as (sampling depth/full ice length) × 100, during winter and spring from coastal Alaskan sites. This dataset was collected between the years 2003 and 2021 from several studies (Table 1). Each point represents the average value of the corresponding variable at a 2% depth interval. Winter samples are from November to February, while spring was considered as March to June.

NO_x concentrations increased to nearly 400 µmol L⁻¹ in the bottommost millimeters.

4. Discussion

4.1. Nutrient sources and regional variability

Nutrient concentrations at the ocean-ice interface vary regionally and interannually in the Arctic due to advection and mixing of different water masses, biological production, local processes, and inputs that can modify surface waters, for example, winter remineralization, coastal dynamics, and riverine inputs (Gosselin et al., 1985; Cota et al., 1987; Duarte et al., 2021). These factors collectively contribute to the complex and region-specific dynamics that influence nutrient distribution within sea ice and the underlying seawater.

Large spatial (pan-Arctic) nutrient patterns are determined strongly by the distinct nutrient composition and influence of the different major water masses (Pacific Water versus Atlantic Water; Figure 7). Additionally, the Arctic Ocean receives around 10% of global river runoff (Carmack et al., 2006; 2015; Tremblay et al., 2015). Freshwater inputs, such as glacial meltwater and river runoff, can influence nutrient concentrations in sea ice and sub-ice waters, especially in coastal regions (Fransson et al., 2015; 2023). Runoff from major rivers transports nutrients from large catchment areas, providing an additional source to the shelf seas downstream (Lee et al., 2023).

However, freshwater input also increases stratification of the upper water column, which inhibits vertical mixing, limiting the upward transport of nutrients from deeper layers (Carmack et al., 2015; Williams et al., 2025). Furthermore, terrestrial runoff, coastal systems and atmospheric deposition also supply nutrients (St. Pierre et al., 2021; Tuerena et al., 2021; Williams et al., 2021; Arrigo et al., 2024).

Pacific Water entering the Arctic Ocean through Bering Strait is fresher and has higher nutrient concentrations, particularly Si(OH)₄, than Atlantic Water (Jones et al., 1998; Giesbrecht et al., 2022; Kinney et al., 2022; Tremblay et al., 2002), accounting for more than 60% of the Si(OH)₄ advected into the Arctic Ocean (Torres-Valdés et al., 2013; Tremblay et al., 2015). The Chukchi Sea and coastal Alaskan waters (sampled near Utqiagvik, formerly known as Barrow) are located within the inflow shelf influenced by advection of Pacific Water, while vertical convection mechanisms along the shallow shelf and deeper basin areas can greatly impact the surface nutrient distribution of these regions (Zhao et al., 2006; Zhuang et al., 2018; 2021). Accordingly, the highest Si(OH)₄ concentrations in bottom ice and sub-ice water were recorded in the Chukchi Sea and coastal Alaskan sites, respectively (Table S3), with low N:Si ratio in both bottom ice and sub-ice water (Table S5). However, there was high interannual variability between the studies.

Figure 6. Millimeter-scale vertical distributions of chl *a* and NO_x concentrations in bottom sea ice, Resolute Passage. High resolution profiles of bottom-ice chl *a* and NO_x concentrations in first-year sea ice at different times in May 1986–1987, in Resolute Passage (data from Smith et al., 1990).

On the opposite side of the Arctic, warm, salty, and nutrient-replete Atlantic waters enter the Arctic Ocean via the Barents Sea opening and through Fram Strait in the West Spitsbergen Current (Rudels et al., 2015; Renner et al., 2023). Although Atlantic inflow waters have lower Si(OH)₄ concentrations than the Pacific inflow (Codispoti et al., 2013; Tremblay et al., 2015), this water is an important nutrient source for the Arctic Ocean. In particular, Atlantic Water contributes to elevated NO_x levels in inflow shelf regions. For example, the highest sub-ice NO_x concentrations were observed in Svalbard fjord (Table S3). Additionally, the Svalbard fjord system receives substantial terrestrial input (McGovern et al., 2020; Santos-Garcia et al., 2022; Forgereau et al., 2023). This influence is reflected in the elevated N:Si ratios observed within the Atlantic inflow shelf regions (Table S5), with interannual variability reflecting seasonal differences in the timing of sampling (Table S2).

The central Arctic Ocean includes two major basins, the Eurasian and Amerasian basins, separated by the Lomonosov Ridge; the Eurasian basin is further subdivided into the Nansen and Amundsen basins by the Gakkel Ridge (Schauer et al., 2002; Carmack et al., 2015). The Nansen Basin is primarily influenced by Atlantic Water which flows beneath a strongly stratified surface layer formed via freshwater supply (Rudels et al., 2015). The Amundsen Basin is largely influenced by cold and fresh Siberian shelf water transported in the Transpolar drift in the upper ocean (Paffrath et al., 2021; Kohlbach et al., 2024; 2025; Laukert et al., 2025). Although the Transpolar drift transports shelf-derived nutrients and sediment material, biological uptake and mixing deplete the nutrient concentrations by the time this water reaches the Amundsen Basin (Kipp et al., 2018; Polyakov et al., 2020), resulting in relatively low concentrations (Table S3). Unlike other nutrients, some of the Siberian rivers contain high Si(OH)₄ concentrations (Debyser et al., 2024), contributing to elevated Si(OH)₄ levels in the Amundsen Basin (Table S3). The Canada Basin is part of the Amerasian Basin. It is influenced by Pacific Water yet is typically observed to be nutrient-limited due to strong stratification enhanced by

riverine inputs and sea-ice melt (Bluhm et al., 2015; Kohlbach et al., 2025).

The outflow shelves of the Arctic, particularly in regions like Baffin Bay and the western Greenland Sea, play a critical role in the export of cold Arctic water masses to the North Atlantic. Cold Arctic outflow water and warm re-circulated Atlantic waters meet on the Northeast Greenland Shelf and flow southward with the East Greenland Current. For example, Young Sound (a fjord in Northeast Greenland), develops a three-layer structure in summer: cold at the bottom, fresh Polar Water in the intermediate layer, and topped by a thin surface layer of meltwater and terrestrial runoff, mirroring the shelf stratification (Gjelstrup et al., 2022), which explains the low sub-ice nutrient concentrations measured in Young Sound (Table S3). In Baffin Bay, west of Greenland, a southward flow along the eastern Baffin Island coast brings cold Arctic outflow waters to the Labrador Sea, whereas the West Greenland Current flows northward along eastern Baffin Bay. The latter delivers warm, modified Atlantic waters along the West Greenland shelf (Burgers et al., 2020), contributing high concentrations of NO_x relative to Si(OH)₄ that can mix into outflowing waters (Tremblay et al., 2002; Oziel et al., 2019). A similar pattern of greater NO_x concentrations and N:Si ratios was evident in Baffin Bay bottom-ice and sub-ice water samples relative to that of eastern Greenland (Figure 2 and Table S3).

Vertical mixing, often driven by wind and storms, can erode the pycnocline, bringing nutrient-rich deep water to the surface (Tremblay et al., 2008). For example, wind-induced Ekman transport brings nutrient-replete water to the ocean-ice interface along coastal regions and/or ice edges, where it has the potential to enhance primary production (Alexander and Niebauer, 1981; Mundy et al., 2009; Williams and Carmack, 2015; Muilwijk et al., 2024). Upwelling is especially prominent along continental shelf breaks, such as coastal areas of the Beaufort Sea (Williams and Carmack, 2008). The Beaufort Sea is an oligotrophic system, but an underlying intermediate layer of Pacific Water containing comparatively high nutrient concentrations can be upwelled intermittently along shelf margins

Figure 7. Schematic map of the Arctic Ocean with major ocean currents and study results by region. Shown are the major ocean currents, Atlantic inflow (red arrows) and Pacific inflow and Arctic outflow (blue arrows), with key regional currents labeled: Transpolar Drift (TD), Baffin Current (BC), West Greenland Current (WGC), East Greenland Current (EGC), and North Atlantic Current (NAC). Boxes provide bottom sea-ice chl *a* and nutrient concentrations (mean ± standard deviation; see Table S3 for *n* values) by region. The map was adapted from Carmack et al. (2015).

and edges of the sea-ice cover under favorable winds (Williams and Carmack, 2008; Mundy et al., 2009). Consequently, greater averaged sub-ice and sea-ice NO_x concentrations were observed in Beaufort Sea but with high variability (Tremblay et al., 2011; Alou-Font et al., 2013; Table S2).

Tidal forcing and sub-ice turbulence can also greatly influence nutrient availability to the bottom-ice algal community (Gosselin et al., 1985). Under-ice turbulent flow at the ocean-ice interface enhances heat and fluid movement across the boundary layer (Feltham et al., 2002) and, therefore, increases the flux of nutrients between the ocean and bottom-ice layer. Tidal current intensity is influenced strongly by bathymetry in shallow regions (Sun et al., 2019) and differs largely for different Arctic areas.

For example, in the CAA, the water column is stratified with cold, relatively fresh, and nutrient-depleted surface waters, underlain by nutrient-replete waters of Pacific origin (Cota et al., 1987). The CAA contains constricted waterways and sills that can increase sub-ice currents locally, thereby increasing mixing across the pycnocline and enhancing ocean-ice heat flux (Hannah et al., 2009; Melting et al., 2015) which, in turn, increase nutrient fluxes (Cota et al., 1987; Dalman et al., 2019). Resolute Passage is located in the center of the CAA. There, tidal mixing processes entrain nutrient-replete waters of Pacific origin to the surface, making this region highly productive (Michel et al., 2006; Mundy et al., 2014). Physical enhancement of nutrient fluxes is the likely explanation for this region showing the highest average sub-ice and bottom-

ice nutrient concentrations, as well as bottom-ice chl *a* concentrations relative to other Arctic regions (Table S3 and **Figure 2**).

In contrast to Resolute Passage, Cambridge Bay is nutrient-limited where surface waters are influenced additionally by local runoff (Pogorzelec et al., 2017; Williams et al., 2021). Freshwater input to Cambridge Bay comes from relatively local northern rivers without substantial new nutrient delivery (Izett et al., 2022). Combined with melting ice and overall precipitation exceeding evaporation, which adds freshwater sources to the surface (McLaughlin et al., 2004), the re-supply of new nutrients via advection and mixing is limited due to the resultant stable halocline (Williams et al., 2025). This stratification leads to the nutrient-depleted surface waters in Cambridge Bay (Campbell et al., 2016; Back et al., 2021); therefore, very low sub-ice and bottom-ice NO_x concentrations were noted in Cambridge Bay (Table S3 and **Figure 2**).

4.2. Influence of ice algae on nutrient concentrations

Chl *a* and nutrient concentrations in different regions vary seasonally due to nutrient availability, uptake stoichiometry, bacterial remineralization, and variations in algal bloom state, including its timing, phase, and magnitude. Regional differences in chl *a* reflect variations in light, grazing, and nutrient dynamics, while methodological differences and sampling times between studies also contribute to variability. We note that in areas with greater sea-ice NO_x concentrations, NO_x increased concomitantly with increasing chl *a* concentrations (**Figure 3b**). Furthermore, NO_x decreased with chl *a* concentrations toward the termination of the ice algal bloom, yielding significant positive correlations between NO_x and chl *a* concentrations (**Figure 4**). This pattern was relatively common at the pan-Arctic scale and suggests that ice algae store excess NO_x (luxury uptake) as intracellular pools that are released during melt-processing of ice cores due to osmotic shock (Cota et al., 1990; Smith et al., 1990). Indeed, Mundy et al. (2025) recently documented averaged intracellular NO_x pools of 68.2 ± 41.6 fmol cell⁻¹ ($n = 17$), concluding that bottom-ice NO_x measurements were directly proportional at 1:1 to intracellular pools of sea-ice algae. Hence, the established sea-ice nutrient protocol of directly melting sea ice without the addition of filtered seawater provides a measurement which is the combination of ambient and intracellular dissolved inorganic nitrogen.

Intracellular nitrate storage by diatoms, the dominant ice algal taxa in the Arctic (Poulin et al., 2011; van Leeuwe et al., 2018) likely represents an important NO_x pool for both freshwater and marine ecosystems (Stief et al., 2022). NO_x storage can provide many potential benefits to ice algae, including (1) dissimilatory reduction, acting as an electron acceptor (Kamp et al., 2011; 2016) to assist in survival through the dark winter period and potentially anoxic conditions in Arctic sea ice in late spring (Rysgaard and Glud, 2004); (2) assimilatory nitrate reduction and buildup of cellular biomass, which can extend the spring ice algal bloom under, for example, a tidally pulsed

nutrient supply (Mundy et al., 2025); and (3) electron sink during periods of high light intensity (e.g., during sea-ice melt; Mundy et al., 2011) to prevent the risk of generating excess reactive oxygen species (Lomas and Glibert, 1999). As an alternative explanation for the accumulation of NO_x in sea ice with increasing algal biomass, several studies have suggested that the high amount of exopolymeric substances produced by ice algae and bacteria increases brine viscosity as well as adsorption of some ions, potentially trapping NO_x within the sea-ice biofilm (Krembs et al., 2011; Steele et al., 2014; Roukaerts et al., 2021). Furthermore, NO_x can also accumulate in sea ice from intense biological nitrogen recycling within the ice (Fripiat et al., 2017; Henley et al., 2023), with approximately 60% of summer Arctic basin nitrate being produced biologically (Clark et al., 2020). However, in this study, NO_x concentrations decreased as chl *a* concentrations leveled off in April in the identified nitrogen-limited zone of Cambridge Bay (**Figure 3b**). This seasonal decline in NO_x concentration could be attributed partly to biological utilization of intracellular pools during periods of low nutrient supply, suggesting that negative correlations between NO_x and chl *a* could indicate nutrient limitation (**Figure 4**). Furthermore, modeled intracellular NO_x concentrations (Figure S2) showed similar magnitudes compared to bottom-ice NO_x concentrations, except for Cambridge Bay, which supports the important contribution of intracellular NO_x pools during blooms in different regions while highlighting region-specific mechanisms to be considered.

PO₄ accumulation in bottom ice as the bloom progresses suggests that ice algae also store PO₄ intracellularly (Cota et al., 1990; Yamaguchi et al., 2015), as documented in many different microalgal taxa (Dyhrman, 2016). Intracellular PO₄ storage may explain why the strongest and most consistent positive correlations across the pan-Arctic were observed between PO₄ and chl *a* concentrations (**Figure 4**). Furthermore, the lower N:P ratios observed in sea-ice relative to sub-ice samples could be influenced by enhanced ice algal uptake (Arrigo, 2005; Yamaguchi et al., 2015; Van der Linden et al., 2020).

Similarly to NO_x and PO₄, accumulation of Si(OH)₄ in the bottom ice indicated that ice algae could also store Si(OH)₄ intracellularly. However, the increase with bloom progression and significant correlations with chl *a* concentrations were not as consistent across pan-Arctic sites (**Figures 3 and 4**). Inadequate attention to thawing can result in a large negative and variable bias in Si(OH)₄ determinations if samples have been stored by freezing (Macdonald et al., 1986; Grasshoff et al., 1999). The loss of dissolved silicon to non-reactive forms after freezing samples cannot be overlooked. Accordingly, the inconsistency in correlation with chl *a* concentration could be a function of storage method of Si(OH)₄ samples, as improper thawing or insufficient thawing time of frozen nutrient samples may impact the measurement (Macdonald et al., 1986). Also suggested is that accumulation of Si(OH)₄ is less than other nutrients in sea ice due to slower rates of diatom frustule dissolution (Henley et al., 2023). However, diatoms are capable of Si(OH)₄ uptake that can exceed

saturation levels (2 mM of $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$) by an order of magnitude, well above ambient concentrations (Martin-Jézéquel et al., 2000). Even though the specific storage mechanism of intracellular $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ is yet to be resolved (Hildebrand et al., 2018), $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ does not get stored in vacuoles like nitrate. Instead, it is transported to specific intracellular compartments known as silica deposition vesicles or silicalemma (Hildebrand and Lerch, 2015), which have been suggested to prevent release of $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ during core melt-processing (Mundy et al., 2025). If correct, then this suggestion helps to explain the weaker and less consistent correlations between $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ and chl *a* concentrations, as well as the higher N:Si ratios in bottom ice relative to the sub-ice water. Other than intracellular accumulation, bacterial hydrolysis of the organic matrix surrounding diatom frustules can expose silica to under-saturated brine, enhancing dissolution (Bidle and Azam, 1999). However, silica dissolution rates are highly temperature-dependent, and the low temperatures of sea-ice brine channels are expected to limit both the dissolution of diatom frustules and the activity of bacterial hydrolytic enzymes (Gnanadesikan and Toggweiler, 1999; Michel et al., 2002; Groudieva et al., 2004; Showalter and Deming, 2021).

NH_4 is either directly excreted by heterotrophs or produced by the remineralization and photochemical degradation of organic compounds released by organisms or from decaying organic matter, including exopolymeric substances (Cota et al., 1987; Riedel et al., 2007; Miller and Wheeler, 2012). Heterotrophic biological activity can contribute, on average, 67% of NH_4 concentrations in newly formed sea ice (Riedel et al., 2007). NH_4 is the preferred nutrient for algal uptake because it can diffuse passively into cells, unlike NO_x , which requires energy for active transport and reduction, with low sea-ice temperatures further limiting nitrate uptake (Dortch, 1990). NH_4 likely supports ice algal production in the regions where NO_x is limited, for example, along the Alaskan coast, coastal Beaufort Sea, and Cambridge Bay. The declining concentrations of NH_4 with increasing chl *a* levels observed in Cambridge Bay again support the interpretation of the onset of nitrogen limitation in Cambridge Bay (**Figure 3e**). In contrast, the elevated NH_4 accumulation in the Beaufort Sea suggests either remineralization at the sea-ice bottom (Henley et al., 2023) or intracellular storage, as indicated by its significant correlation with chl *a* concentration (Spearman correlation, $p < 0.001$).

With respect to vertical distribution, nutrient concentrations are not homogeneously distributed throughout the ice. Vertical profiles of nutrients varied seasonally in response to the growth of sea-ice algae, changes in light availability, sea-ice and brine dynamics, and nutrient replenishment from the underlying water column. Nutrient concentrations in the sea-ice matrix are initially determined via thermodynamic ice growth processes, whereas the permeable bottommost skeletal layer is influenced by continuous exchange with the underlying water column. As sea ice grows vertically, nutrient exchange between the upper layers and underlying water decreases because the distance from the ice-water interface to the upper layers of the ice increases,

and the upper ice matrix also becomes less permeable, limiting internal convection and diffusion (Golden et al., 2007; Manes and Gradinger, 2009). In winter, nutrient concentrations generally follow salinity gradients due to the absence of significant biological activity or remineralization processes (Petrich and Eicken, 2010), as was observed along the Alaskan coast with low chl *a* concentrations. However, with light availability increasing in spring, the relationship between salinity and nutrient concentration shifted as chl *a* concentrations rose, particularly in the bottom layer of sea ice. NO_x concentrations mirrored the distribution of chl *a*, consistent with the concept of nutrient accumulation influenced by the growth and accumulation of ice algal biomass. This trend is particularly evident in a classic study conducted by Smith et al. (1990) from Resolute Passage during spring. These authors observed the highest chl *a* concentrations ever documented in the Arctic, reaching 30 mg L^{-1} in the bottommost 2 mm of sea ice. The vertical distribution of NO_x concentrations in the bottom few millimeters of sea ice was consistent with chl *a* concentrations, reaching extremely high NO_x concentrations of $400 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$. Smith et al. (1990) were also the first to suggest an intracellular nutrient pool in the ice algae. These observations clearly highlight the significant role of ice algae in influencing dissolved nutrient concentrations within the sea-ice environment.

We infer that sea-ice nutrient measurements during the ice algal bloom are influenced by intracellular nutrient pools released during sample melting due to the osmotic shock. This intracellular nutrient pool can play a critical role in supporting ice algal growth and survival under challenging environmental conditions. For example, intracellular nutrient storage likely helps ice algae partially overcome nutrient limitation by acting as a buffer during periods of low external nutrient supply, although intracellular storage of $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ appears to equate only to the nutrient demand of one cellular division or less (Mundy et al., 2025). With respect to the sea-ice melt method, past datasets have relied predominantly on this measurement, which remains a valuable and widely used technique. However, our data assessment highlights that this method can have some biases. Bulk-ice measurements are effective for the determination of the nitrate pool associated with the ice algal community, as they reflect the near-complete release of intracellular pools (Mundy et al., 2025); however, they likely do not provide accurate determination of $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ availability as diatom frustules or intracellular silica deposition vesicles may not release dissolved $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ upon melting. Sequential extraction methods adapted from marine sediment studies (Pickering et al., 2023) could be explored in future research to better distinguish reactive versus unreactive silica pools in sea ice. Therefore, we suggest incorporating additional methods, for example, analyzing ice-water interface nutrient concentration and direct measurement of intracellular nutrients on intact cells, or developing new methods, such as applying an isohaline melt technique as used for sea-ice bacteria and viruses (Deming and Collins,

2010). These additional methods will help to unravel the role of intracellular nutrient storage and its influence on nutrient dynamics in the sea-ice environment.

5. Summary

This study presents the first comprehensive analysis of sea-ice chl *a* concentrations and nutrient distribution in first-year sea ice and sub-ice waters from a pan-Arctic perspective, focusing on regional, seasonal, and vertical variability. Although nutrient concentrations in bottom sea ice largely followed availability in the underlying water column, there was a clear influence of ice algae on sea-ice nutrient concentrations.

Ice algae utilize nutrients mainly from the water column, where nutrient fluxes to the ice algal community are driven largely by the strength of ocean-ice shear and associated turbulence and by vertical nutrient gradients. The examined dataset reflects that Pacific Water influences the Chukchi Sea and Alaskan coastal waters, contributing high levels of Si(OH)₄ to both sea ice and sub-ice waters, whereas Atlantic inflow shelf regions contain relatively lower Si(OH)₄, but higher NO_x concentrations. In the outflow shelf regions, Baffin Bay exhibited higher nutrient concentrations than Greenland fjord, where eastern Greenland fjords are strongly influenced by terrestrial input. While the upper ocean layer in the Nansen Basin is fed by Atlantic Water, the upper ocean layer of the Amundsen Basin is influenced by the Transpolar drift and Siberian river water, which contain relatively lower nutrient (except Si(OH)₄) concentrations due to consumption by primary producers over shelf seas and dilution with sea-ice melt water, thus explaining nutrient variability across Arctic basins. Locally, high nutrient concentrations found in both sea ice and sub-ice waters in interior shelves (e.g., Resolute Passage) are likely driven by tidal mixing, while the significantly nutrient-depleted areas of Cambridge Bay are influenced strongly by local riverine input.

In addition to physical and environmental factors, ice algae play a key role in regulating nutrient concentrations in the bottom layer of the sea ice. Increasing nutrient concentrations with increasing chl *a* concentrations in bottom sea ice were observed during the bloom across most of the pan-Arctic region. This association suggests that ice algae employ a concentration mechanism for storing nutrients when nutrients are available, while nonsignificant and negative correlations are likely indicative of nutrient limitation. These results highlight the critical role of ice algae in Arctic nutrient cycling, particularly in regulating nutrient availability in bottom ice across the pan-Arctic. While discussing seasonal variability, this study did not consider key environmental variables such as snow and ice thickness, which can impact light availability and influence ice algal productivity and nutrient uptake significantly. Future research could benefit from including additional datasets with seasonal coverage and a greater emphasis on environmental influences. Overall, our assessment enhances the understanding of the complex dynamics between sea-ice algae and nutrient concentrations across the Arctic.

Data accessibility statement

The dataset is publicly available on the CanWIN data repository titled as Pan-Arctic nutrient concentrations in Arctic Ocean (1983-2023) (<https://canwin-datahub.ad.umanitoba.ca/data/dataset/nutrient-dataset>).

Supplemental files

The supplemental files for this article can be found as follows:

Supplemental Material.docx.

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Competing interests

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Author contributions

Contributed to conception and design: FA, CJM, EL, ARJ
Contributed to acquisition of data: FA, EL, ARJ, KC, KBD, AN, RG, EAF, STV, LW, EMJ, AF, MC, LMO, RDM, SHL, MO, BAL

Contributed to analysis and interpretation of data: FA, CJM, EL, ARJ, KBD, PA, RG

Drafted and/or revised the article: FA, EL, ARJ, KC, KBD, PA, AN, RG, EAF, STV, LW, EMJ, AF, MC, LMO, RDM, SHL, MO, BAL, JÉT, MG, CJM

Approved the submitted version for publication: All authors

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